

RESOURCE AND HISTORIOGRAPHY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL INFRASTRUCTURE OF UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the study of rural infrastructure of Uzbekistan through modern trends during the years of independence is a new direction. From this point of view, the study of this area was studied by representatives of a number of leading branches of Science operating in Uzbekistan, whose research includes important information on certain aspects of rural life.

The process of reforms carried out in Uzbekistan during the years of independence is also studied by many foreign scientists. In view of these cases, the researcher Ch.Temirova showed in his research work the study of literature, which served to highlight the topic, from a historiographic point of view, into three groups. They are reflected below.

1. Studies covering historical aspects of the issue;
2. Research and literature created by representatives of the socio-humanitarian sphere;
3. Thematic work of foreign authors.

To the first group directly in the years of independence socio-cultural scientific works were included, in which historical aspects of the field were analyzed as objects of research. As a result of the analysis and study of the research included in this group, studies on socio-economic and cultural-educational issues of the villages of Uzbekistan in the years of independence indicate the peculiarity of the topic of rural social and cultural life in the development of the science of history of Uzbekistan.

Z.Mirzaev, A.Norbekov, R.A. Nosirov, A.A. Mavrulov and yu.The essence of the doctoral issue devoted to the history of the social and cultural sphere of the villages of Uzbekistan of the ergashevas is sufficiently cited. This is evidenced by the fact that the situation, problems of the villages of Uzbekistan in different historical periods, the main directions of rural cultural institutions, rural social development were studied and analyzed from a scientific point of view in historical science by these authors. In Particular, Z.Mirzaev and A.It is observed that the narrative style of the norbekovs ' doctoral dissertation, in particular, theoretically-methodologically, did not completely get rid of the influence of the ideology of the Soviet period.

Also, the periodic limit of doctoral dissertations, the names of which are mentioned above, belongs to the Soviet period, and the exact data presented in them are of significant scientific importance in the comparative study of the socio-cultural situation in the years of independence.

Among the candidate's dissertations devoted to the socio-economic and cultural life of the villages of Uzbekistan, the work of B.N.Uzakov, M.D.Hadzhievas should also be noted. In the research carried out by these authors, the main focus was also on the research of the social life of villages. In recent years, work on the topic of the history of villages can be attributed to the research of E.R.Tilaev, N.K. Kuvvatov and F.J.Yormatov. The dissertation of N.Kuvvatov is mainly devoted to the study of the socio-economic life of the villages of the Kashkadarya region in the Soviet period, while the dissertation of E.Tilaev reflects on economic development, social and spiritual and educational life of the population in the southern regions of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the system of social protection of the population in the southern regions was also reflected in the study of F.Yormatov.

Of particular importance is the work of A.Mavrulov in the research of the history of the cultural sphere in the years of independence on the basis of a new theoretical methodology. During the years of independence, a number of other pamphlets and monographs were also created dedicated to the study of the history of the Soviet period of the social and cultural sphere. For example, in the Monographs of A.Hazratkulov and S.Tursunov, the work carried out in different directions of the social sphere during the Soviet period and their results were analyzed from a new theoretical methodology dotinazar. These works are among the first attempts of the Soviet period to critically study the activities of the social sphere.

The above-mentioned monograph by A.Hazratqulov describes the study of many problems of the social sphere in Uzbekistan in the 70s and 90s, as well as reflections on their elimination. S.Tursunov's monograph problems of improving housing and household conditions of rural people " is valuable for its involvement in the topic under direct study. The author thoroughly studied the activities of the rural housing and household service network and summarizes information about rural housing conditions in the conditions of Soviet rule. In the Monographs of M. Nurmuhammedova and Y.Ergasheva, issues in the cultural sphere and their solution are studied in the villages of Uzbekistan. In particular, the monograph of M. Nurmuhammedova reflects on the human factor and rural social development, cultural and whitening institutions, various folk holidays.

In the historiography of the subject of cultural history, a special place is occupied by the monograph of the Yu.Ergasheva "Kultura Uzbekistana: tendentsii i problemi razvitiya". In this monograph, The History of almost all directions of the cultural sphere was studied in Uzbekistan in the 50-60 years of the 20th century. The author touches on the specific pros and cons of the life of Public Education, the system of secondary and higher education, science, literature and art, cultural and educational institutions and the media in Uzbekistan, in particular in the southern regions.

Studies and literature created by representatives of the socio-humanitarian sphere, which analyzed various aspects of rural infrastructure, were introduced. The topic studied in the studies of T.Abdullaev, Z.Ismailova, I.Ramazonov, M. Eshmatov was analyzed from a philosophical point of view and summarized thoughts on the spiritual image of rural youth, socio-political and spiritual factors of updating the rural lifestyle, the problem of approaching the lives of urban and rural residents. The research of R.Muratov, Z.Khudoyberdiev, R.Egamberdiev, B.Yangiboev, Sh.Qarshiev is devoted to the study of rural economic life, which provides information on the provision of rural residents with food, light industrial products in

rural demography, general state of the socio-economic and cultural-educational sphere, rural and market, Social Protection System in the village, rural culture and public organizations, family, ecology and health issues. Among them, first of all, it should be noted the work of the likes of M.Islamov, A.Mamatkazin, Y.Dodoboev, A.Mamadaliyev, A.Juraev, M.Usmanova, U.Umarova, I.Ergashev, M.Kholmatova, S.Safaeva, M.Sadikova, and Sh.Otaboev.

The research of these authors, created in the early years of independence, was analyzed from the point of view of the idea of independence of the social, cultural life of the villages of Uzbekistan. They also examined the process of formation of rural social infrastructure, the conditions of social protection of the rural population during the transition to a market economy, problems in rural cultural and educational institutions, and tried to comprehensively highlight the main essence of rural policy in independent Uzbekistan.

In the historiography of the topic of social and cultural life of the southern regions of Uzbekistan, issues such as the features of the growth of the population of the country's villages, socio-economic problems of demographic processes in the village, the development of social infrastructure are also reflected in the monograph "Demographics of rural areas".

The monograph emphasizes that the rural population of Uzbekistan grew by 139.3% during the period 1989-2005, with the highest rates observed in Surkhandarya and Kashkadarya regions, and that the same regions determine regional characteristics in the demographic development of the Republic. A. Juraev's monograph "Rural and social life" brings a lot of information about the social life of the villages of Kashkadarya and Surkhandarya regions. In the monograph of the doctor of political science, professor I.Ergashev, the role of villages in the political-social life of society, the reforms carried out in villages in state politics and their results, issues of spiritual renewal of villages are analyzed from a political-philosophical point of view. In his monograph, The author explores the theme of independence and rural politics by comparing the past and present of the village. The work gives the same assessment as the work on social protection of rural residents in Uzbekistan: "It was noted that it is important for the state to take a stratified approach to social assistance to rural residents of the Republic, to accurately take into account the nature of each place, the needs of the layers of the population for social assistance".

In conclusion, it should be noted that kerakkai, the location and historiography of the infrastructure of the villages of the Southern Region of Uzbekistan are sufficiently illuminated. However, the fact that the opinions expressed in terms of the tavsional tractator remain merely a matter of Statistics encourages a further reanalysis of the subject of this period.

References:

1. Темирова Ч. Ўзбекистон қишлоқлари ривожланишининг ижтимоий-маданий аспекти: ҳолати ва муаммолар (Қашқадарё ва Сурхондарё вилоятлари мисолида 1991-2008 йй.). Автореф. дис. ... т.ф.н. –Тошкент, 2010
2. Мирзаев З. Культурная жизнь села Узбекистана: состояние, особенности и проблемы (60-е- середина 70-х годов). Автореф. дис. ... докт. ист. наук. –Ташкент, 1991.
3. Нарбеков А. Развитие сельских учреждений культуры Узбекистана и их место в формировании нового человека. (1975-1985 гг). Автореф. дис. ... докт. ист. наук. – Ташкент, 1991.

4. Маврулов А.А. Культура Узбекистана на современном этапе: общее состояние. Проблемы. Тенденции развитие (середина 70-х-1990 гг.). Автореф. дис. ... докт. ист. наук. –Ташкент, 1991.
5. Насыров Р.А. Социальное развитие села Узбекистана. (1965-1985). Автореф. дис. ... докт. ист. наук. –Ташкент, 1994.
6. Эргашева Ю.А. Культура Узбекистана: состояние, тенденции и проблемы развитие (50-60-е годы). Автореф. дис. ... докт. ист. наук. –Ташкент, 1998.
7. Узоков Б.Н. Социальные аспекты развитие орошаемого земледелия в Узбекистана в 60-е нач. 70-х гг (на материалах южных областей). Автореф. дис. ... канд. ист. наук. – Ташкент, 1992.
8. Хаджиева М.Д. Социальное развитие села Узбекистана в конце 70-х и начале 80-х годов: опыт и проблемы. Автореф. дис. ... канд. ист. наук. –Ташкент, 1992.
9. Тилаев Э.Р. Мустақиллик йилларида Ўзбекистоннинг ижтимоий-иқтисодий ва маданий ҳаётидаги ўзгаришлар (Жанубий вилоятлар мисолида). Автореф. дис. ... т.ф.н. – Тошкент, 2010.
10. Қувватова Н.Қ. XX асрнинг 20-80 йилларида Ўзбекистон қишлоқларининг ижтимоий-иқтисодий ҳаёти (Қашқадарё вилояти мисолида). Автореф. дис. ... т.ф.н. – Тошкент, 2010.
11. Ёрматов Ф.Ж. Ўзбекистонда аҳолини ижтимоий ҳимоялаш тизими: ҳолати, шаклланиш жараёни, ривожланиш истиқболлари (1991-2010 йиллар. Жанубий вилоятлар мисолида). Автореф. дис. ... т.ф.н. –Тошкент, 2010.